

educators. By integrating peer learning into extracurricular programs, schools can create a dynamic and supportive environment that nurtures both language acquisition and personal growth.

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THE ROLE OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This article draws attention to the importance of competency-based design in the educational environment, discusses the ways to improve the situation with subject-specific competence in elementary school students and maintain their competence.*

***Keywords.** Education, upbringing, competence, competency-based orientation, linguistic competence, native speaker, elementary school students.*

Introduction. In today's rapidly changing and developed information and communication technologies, educating the younger generation as highly spiritual and intellectually developed individuals is one of the priority areas of state policy. Reforms in this area are being implemented within the framework of the Law “On Education” and similar laws, as well as large-scale nationwide programs, and are recognized by developed countries of the world and international organizations. First of all, the effectiveness of the educational process depends on the high-quality implementation of the requirements of the State Educational Standards and curricula, developed on the basis of today's demands, the needs of society, and the development trends of science and technology.

Main part 1. In solving the problem of forming the foundations of a scientific worldview in students in the process of learning English, the material that serves as the basis for teaching English at school is of particular value. The authenticity of the material, its ideological orientation and artistic expressiveness affect the thinking and feelings of students, expand their knowledge of the environment, cultivate interest in the language and the people who created it, increase the level of general development of students and influence the formation of their personal qualities and worldview. In recent years, the requirements for the content of school English textbooks and manuals published for teachers have increased significantly in quantity and quality, taking into account precisely these factors.

The main criteria for the material are the knowledge-enriching value of the text and individual sentences, lexical and stylistic accuracy, thematic diversity, connection with various aspects of life, ideological and thematic orientation of the texts, and suitability for younger students. The implementation of such requirements, along with the development of the main types of speech activity in high school students, involves solving the following important issues.

Main part 2. Today, the terms competence and linguistic competence approach have entered education and are rapidly gaining popularity. In linguistics, this term was first used in the middle of the 20th century and was interpreted as a

set of knowledge, skills and competencies focused on activities in the process of using language. In this context, the concepts of competence and competence approach are noted as factors indicating effectiveness in education.

The levels of competence (or levels of competence) acquired in each subject at a particular educational stage are the ability to apply the acquired knowledge, practical skills, and personal qualities to temporary activities in a certain field. This is not only a set of acquired theoretical knowledge, skills, and qualifications, but also the level of independent and creative application of the acquired theoretical and practical knowledge in practice.

Conclusion. In the modern education system, more attention is paid to educating a free personality through the formation of competency-based knowledge, forming the ability to think independently in future generations, acquiring and applying knowledge, quickly and thoroughly thinking through decisions and clearly planning actions, effective cooperation in various groups, and openness to new contacts. In this regard, the widespread use of methods for developing students' talents, the use of new pedagogical tools such as interactive methods and multimedia in the lesson process also gives effective results.

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